

BRAZILIAN AGRORESIDUAL COCONUT FIBER (*Cocos nucifera*) AS POTENTIAL NON-CONVENTIONAL RAW MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

The Brazilian coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) industry is the 5th largest fruit producer in the world, generating huge amounts of husks residues. The inadequate end destination causes contamination and socio-environmental risks. There is a growing need for the use of alternative raw materials resources in the Brazilian petrochemical dependent industry. Considering sustainability guidelines, this research aimed at the analysis of coconut fibers as potential raw materials. To cover these aspects, a Systematic Review of the Literature (SRL) based on the concepts of industrial ecology was carried out. Studies have been developed with Brazilian coconut fiber, such as bio sorbent for textile dyes; handicrafts; green composites, and copolymers.

KEYWORDS

Coconut fiber; Agroresidual; Non-conventional materials; Sustainability; Sustainable materials.

INTRODUCTION

The Brazilian agro-industrial chain generates about 291 million/tons/year of waste. The coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) palm plays an important economic and social role in the Brazilian agroindustry. It is the 5th largest fruit producer in the world (Brainer, 2018; Simone et al., 2020). Although, the accumulation of coconut post-consumption represents a problem for the health management of rural and urban areas (Martins et al., 2016). The husks, when deposited incorrectly, occupy large spaces with decomposition responsible for gases' contribution to global warming and diseases (Castilhos, 2012). The industry processes a small portion of coconut by-products, which generates about 80% to 85% of the gross bulky weight (Ferreira-Leitão et al., 2017; Martins et al., 2016).

The need for renewable manufactured products is a major challenge for the Brazilian industry dependent on petrochemical resources (Alarcon et al., 2021; Atiqah et al., 2020; Hoque et al., 2021; Izwan et al., 2021). The use, processing, and characterization of agro-industrial wastes is a great opportunity to generate value and develop by-products and co-products in materials with competitive mechanical properties, lightness, and biodegradability of low-cost natural fibers to replace petroleum-based fibers in composites (Berté, 2009; Dahiya et al., 2020; Embrapa, 2018; Shahid-ul-Islam et al., 2013). Coconut fibers stand out due to their intense abundance of residues, and their physicochemical properties of high quality, low cost, low density, and biodegradability (RAZERA, 2006). Therefore, there are alternatives

for the reuse of these productive residues, such as their use in different applications (Martins et al., 2016). Indeed, markets for products based on agro-fiber present great potential for application in absorbents, technical textiles, geotextiles, filters, biocomposites, and other automotive and construction sectors (Shishoo, 2007).

Considering sustainability guidelines, this study aims to investigate Brazilian agro-industrial residues as potential raw materials with the extraction process and physical-chemical characterization of coconut fiber (*Cocos nucifera*). Based on Industrial Ecology concepts, the methodology through Systematic Literature Review (RSL) and bibliometric analysis of data. The agricultural biomass related to the main crops presents characteristics making it suitable to be applied for textiles, such as natural fibers and polymers; in biosorbents for industrial effluents; cellulose obtention, and reinforcement material in composites. Studies have been developed with Brazilian coconut fiber, such as bio sorbent for textile dyes; handicrafts; green composites, and copolymers.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology was based on a bibliographic survey and analysis by Systematic Literature Review (RSL) followed by bibliometrics. According to Denyer and Tranfield, 2009, the RSL is an important scientific tool that groups, evaluates contributions, selects, analyzes, and synthesizes data that allow obtaining concrete evidence for known and uncovering new goals (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009). Bibliometric analysis, on the other hand, through variable studies, provides guidance and dynamics, through performance analysis and scientific mapping of research fields and cognitive structures, such as the study of link frequencies, implemented in this work (Cobo et al., 2011; Macias-Chapula, 1998).

The review process involved aspects of planning, execution, and analysis of results (BA and Charters, 2007). The focus, based on industrial ecology concepts (Giannetti, B. F.; Almeida, 2006; Lifset and Graedel, 2015), examined research on the use of coconut wastes for the development of sustainable materials. The results were compared with data from the Brazilian Ministries of Agriculture and Environment and related associations.

To generate the database, the searches performed used the variation of the terms “coconut”, “coir”, “coconut fiber”, “waste”, “fiber”, “materials” and “applications” limited to Brazil (from May 2021 to June 2021 that encompass the years from 2007 to 2020). The next items discussed respectively: (i) the dynamics of scarcity and availability of alternative materials; (ii) Brazilian scenario of biomass productive insertion with varieties and important economic aspects from coconut palm trees; and (iii) possibilities for coconut fiber commons applicability’s and their related applications of coconut fiber in Brazilian development researches.

RESULTS

Raw Material Obtaining

Food supply chain waste is the most available biomass resource subject to circular processing. Residues such as peels, seeds, leaves, and other fruit and vegetable residues have been scientifically proven to be a viable and valuable raw material for countless products (Sillanpää and Ncibi, 2019; Wiesmeth, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c). For Laudes Foundation (2021), the valorization of these residues offers great potential to reduce extensive harvesting, fires, and their environmental and climatic impacts; generate new low-cost additive revenue streams for farming communities; and activate a new, scalable and environmentally sustainable fiber source for the growing apparel and fashion industry. Among the sources, vegetable fibers have the main advantage in sustainable appeal (Lopes et al., 2021).

Sustainability has become an important aspect of the manufacturing industry and research interest (Kalita et al., 2021).

Coconut (*Cocos nucifera*.) is an important multifunctional crop in the tropics, cultivated in more than 90 countries, considered the most useful tree to man, each part of the palm during history has been put to active economic use by humanity (Adkins et al., 2010). However, on average in Brazil, about 7 million tons of coconut are discarded per year, the husks, processing, and consumption residues, when deposited incorrectly, occupy large spaces with decomposition responsible for causing socio-environmental risks to society (Castilhos, 2012).

The fragmentation of supply chains makes the concentration and organization of control, while there is material disposal (Scheffer, 2012). The sum of factors evidences the selection of fibers as a variable intervention in the carbon footprint and global climate change (Nayak et al., 2021; Peters et al., 2015). One of the main difficulties in the conversion process of biomass into products is the transport and storage protocol, in addition to the knowledge of the operational techniques that should be applied (Onu and Mbohwa, 2021a; Warf, 2014). As claimed by Onu & Mbohwa (2021c), the world's largest production crops such as sugarcane, corn, rice, and wheat are in discussion as food and fuel commodities as well as due to their important source of hemicellulose and lignocellulose industrial manufacture. Waste treatment and disposal are only part of agricultural waste management systems (Loehr, 1974).

The water content, pathogenic potential, and biological instability make the disposal of waste difficult to control, directing it generally to animal feed (Dietrich et al., 2016). In the same way, the administration of large residues leads agrarian communities to opt for low-cost and low-effort options, such as burning to clear the scums for the next harvests (Textile Horizons International, 1993). For Laudes Foundation (2021), domestic uses such as forage, animal bedding, mulch, and compost use a small part of the waste. Among the benefits of using waste materials are the protection and maintenance of natural resources, protection of human health, and reduction in resource extraction (Ahmad et al., 2021).

In the Brazilian scenario, agribusiness has gained great notoriety in the context of studies and political-economic-institutional focus (ABRA, 2013). The amount of biomass produced in Brazil is significant, reaching 1 Gt in 2030 (Moraes et al., 2017). There is a movement of research in the country to create viable alternatives for the relocation of waste (M. Martelli-Tosi et al., 2017; Martelli-Tosi et al., 2017). According to the Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (EMBRAPA), the industrial processing of agricultural biomass from waste can be distributed in the generation of materials (polymers, resins, and fibers), energy, food and animal feed, chemical inputs (biofertilizers, surfactants, esters, acids organic) and biofuels (ethanol, biodiesel, and biogas) (Júnior, 2020). However, its application in by-products is mainly used for rural energy, animal feed, and disposal in the field (Liu et al., 2015). Araújo et al. (2019), evaluating parameters, which consider the chemical composition, growth rate, and disposition, state that soy straw is the most suitable residue to be used as raw material for the production of cellulosic-based materials, followed by sugarcane leaf, corn husk, sugarcane straw, and bagasse, revealing that the main crops in the country are the most suitable residually.

The coconut issue in Brazil

Coconut palm is a tropical crop, widely distributed in Asia, Africa, Latin America, and the Pacific region. (Siqueira et al., 2002). It is considered one of the most important trees in the world, a base and sustenance in coastal and island ecosystems. Responsible for generating employment in all its exploration and commercialization stages, which generates income in about 90 countries, its fruits can be consumed *in natura* or processed in more than 100 different products and by-products. (Ageitec,

2012). This large amount and variety of products obtained from this plant make it popularly known as "tree of life", "tree of well-being" and "tree of heaven"(Cambui et al., 2007; Mathai, 2005a).

The world-harvested area of coconut is about 12 million hectares, producing 61.1 million tons. (Brainer, 2018). World coconut production is concentrated in three countries, Indonesia (30.1%), Philippines (24.7%) and India (19.0%). Brazil occupies the place of 5th largest producer, participating in 4.5% of the total produced, after Sri Lanka (Brainer and Ximenes, 2020).

Production is mostly carried out by small and medium-sized family farmers (about 85%), to a lesser extent, by large agro-industrial companies (Nordeste Rural, 2015). When analyzing the historical productive behavior of coconut, expressive growth is visible. Total world production has increased substantially from 35 million tonnes around 1980 to nearly 50 million tonnes (Dam, 2002) mainly in the Brazilian market, due to technological incentives (Fontes et al., 2002). In the periods from 1990 to 2009, Brazil went from the tenth to the 4th largest producer in the world, and the prospects for growth both in productivity and in the scope of the market tend to grow (Martins and Jesus Junior, 2011)

Currently, Brazil is the 5th largest producer, with a share of 4.5% of the world produced, highlighting an annual growth of 0.8% of the harvested area and 0.1% of the world production, in the last decade (Brainer and Ximenes, 2020; Simone et al., 2020). This increase in production is mainly due to productivity, as while the cultivated area grew by 13.2% between 1990 and 2015, production and productivity increased by 143.2 and 114.8% (Brainer, 2018).

Studies in the area estimate that, on average, 1 hectare of coconut occupies 3 people directly employed and each direct job provides four jobs indirectly (Cuenca, 2016). Considering the area harvested in Brazil in 2019 of 186,950 ha, they generate 560,850 direct jobs and 2,243,400 indirect jobs along the coconut production chain. This is relevant because small properties (less than 10 ha) of family agriculture are predominant, which are characterized by the use of semi-extractive production systems (Fontes, 2006).

Despite the subsequent loss in recent years due to climatic adversities, Brazil has the 6th largest area in the world, standing out in the Value of production of 929,594 thousand reais (2019); Quantity produced 1,553,966 thousand fruits (2019); Establishments of 37,515 Units (2017); Number of feet 25,170 thousand units (2017) (IBGE, 2020, 2021a, 2021b).

However, the increase in consumption and industrial production of coconut contributes to the generation of about 2.7 million tons per year, of which 74.5% are green coconut, which is more difficult to degrade than dry coconut (Simone et al., 2020). It is discarded on average in Brazil, about 7 million tons of coconut per year. There is a big issue in the post-consumption of coconut in Brazil regarding the accumulation of this material, which represents a problem for the sanitary management of several rural and urban areas, in addition to being harmful to the environment when dumped in sanitary landfills. (Martins et al., 2016; Mourão et al., 2016) .

The bark, when deposited incorrectly, in addition to occupying large spaces, decomposition generated is responsible for the production and release of methane, a major contributor to global warming. (Passos, 2005). For the processing of this waste, the research agency EMBRAPA Agroindústria Tropical in partnership with metallurgical companies has developed technologies for the transformation of the bark into powder and fiber, in a possible opportunity to generate income for the producer and reduce the impacts generated by the increase in waste. (Correa, 2006a; Júnior, 2020; Rosa, 2002).

The coconut fiber

Coconut fibers belong to the lignocellulosic class, composed mainly of cellulose and lignin (Mathai, 2005a). Coconut husk (a source of fiber) has been treated as waste for many years. Scientific technologies and the characteristics of elasticity, durability, and resistance to traction and humidity, made possible its use as a possible industrial raw material for Brazil. (Correa, 2006b) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Coconut Structure (Mattos et al., 2013).

The green coconut husk contains: (i) epicarp (outer layer), the “husk” of the fruit; (ii) mesocarp, located between epicarp and endocarp; (iii) endocarp (stone layer) more internal than the pericarp, rigid part that surrounds the seed, has three circular depressions at the base (carpels) forming the embryo; (iv) albumen, tissue with nourishing substances in the seed (Carvalho, 2009). The mesocarp is the thick part and fiber source of the fruit. It can contain from 3 to 5 cm in thickness, consisting of a fraction of short and long fibers and another fraction called powder, which is aggregated to the fibers (Rosa, 2002) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Coconut Fruit and Coconut fiber *in natura* (Mylena Uhlig Siqueira).

Coconut fibers are classified into three varieties: (i) finer and shorter fiber, (ii) moderately coarser and longer fiber, and (iii) harder and very long fiber (Figure 3) (Dam, 2002; Madhav et al., 2018; Mishra and Basu, 2020b).

Figure 3: Long and short coconut brown fibers (Adapted from Correa, 2006a).

For the author, the thinnest and shortest fibers are used as filling for mattresses, and the medium-length fibers are those applicable to textiles, as are the harder fibers used for brushes and brooms (Mishra and Basu, 2020a; SAVASTANO JR, 1986).

Characterization, physical and chemical properties of coconut fiber

The fibers of coconut cultivars have different compositions depending on their origin, maturity, and form of extraction. Therefore, similar thermal and mechanical properties are highlighted, which demonstrate the potential to be used on an industrial scale (Jeronimo and Silva, 2013; Martins and Jesus Junior, 2011).

There are different data regarding its chemical composition due to the origin, extraction, location, and cultivation of the fiber of the analyzed fruit (Table 1). They are extracted from the fibrous mesocarp of the fruit and about 20.6% of its chemical composition is related to the number of total extractives (fatty acids, some resins, tannins, gums, sugars, starch, and dyes), 54% Lignin and 25.4% % ash (inorganic matter such as calcium and potassium)(Catunda et al., 2016). Coconut fibers represent approximately 32% of the lignin, 45% of the cellulose, 20% of the hemicelluloses, and 1.3% of the ash (Paz et al., 2017). Lignin represents 37% to 43% of coconut fiber, while cellulose varies from 31% to 37% (Corradini et al., 2009). The high degree of lignin explains its durability and resistance. From cellulose is a possibility of obtaining second-hand ethanol, and ash (Cabral and Santos, 2017). Lignin, present in a large part of the composition of coconut fiber, constitutes a natural binder function, which under suitable conditions of pressure and temperature, can dispense with the use of synthetic resins (Corradini et al., 2009). Being an alternative to the use of conventional adhesives that are based on formaldehyde, a substance considered toxic and carcinogenic, derived from petroleum These characteristics, among others, such as the optimal levels of porosity, absorption, and resistance to fertilizers, make different applications possible (Aragão et al., 2005).

Table 1: Chemical compositions of coconut fiber (Adapted from Agopyan et al., 2005; Aragao, 2002; Corradini et al., 2009; John et al., 2005; Khalil et al., 2006)

	(Aragao, 2002)	(Corradini et al., 2009)	(Khalil et al., 2006)	(Agopyan et al., 2005; John et al., 2005)
Cellulose (%)	23-43	31-37	44.2	35-60
Lignin (%)	35-45	37-43	32.8	20-48
Hemicellulose (%)	3-12	-	6.4	15-28

The fibrous yarns are highly lignified cellulose, having rough and rigid characteristics. (Mishra and Basu, 2020a). Lignin plays an important role in the physical characteristics of fibers, making them harder and

stiffer than pure lignocellulosic fibers, such as cotton, and harder than other lignocellulosic fibers such as sisal, pineapple, and ramie (Arunachalam, 2012).

In addition to the chemical composition, the physical properties must be mentioned (Rao et al., 2005). These ensure high tensile strength and elongation properties, with advantages including acceptable specific strength properties, high elasticity, low cost, low density, and biodegradability (Martins and Sanches, 2019) (Table 2).

Table 2: Characteristics and properties of coconut fibers (Adapted from Aragao, 2002 and Erhardt, 1976).

Properties	Values
pH	5.4
Electric conductivity	1.8 dS/m
C/N Ratio	132
Density	70 g/L
Total Porosity	95.6%
Water retention	538 mL/L
Assimilable water	19.8%
Length	12 – 33 cm
Diameter	0.05 a 0.4 mm
Resistance	dry: fiber (8-20km). yarn (8-12km). Wet :93% dry resistance
Hygroscopicity	moisture combination 13.00%

These characteristics show its technological potential, even superior to other vegetable fibers, favoring its reuse as an alternative raw material in the composition of new products (Catunda et al., 2016) (Table 3).

Table 3: Chemical composition of some vegetable fibers (Adapted from Faruk et al., 2012 and Silva, 2003).

	Cellulose (%)	Hemicellulose (%)	Lignin (%)	Extractives (%)
Coconut	32-43	0.15-0.25	40-45	-
Sisal	65	12	9.9	2
Rami	68.6-76.2	13-16	0.6-0.7	0.3
Jute	61-71	14-20	12-13	0.5
Hemp	68	15	10	0.8
Linen	71	18.6-20.6	2.2	1.5
Pineapple Leaf	70-82	18	5-10	-
Banana Tree leaf	60-65	6-8	5-10	-
Sugarcane Bagasse	32-48	19-24	23-32	-

Coconut fiber cells are oval with small air cavities near the center of the filaments (about one-third of the fiber volume is filled by this air). Air gives rise to elasticity (resilience), buoyancy in the water, and increased time for water penetration into fibers (Mathai, 2005a). For the author, this indicates that the properties of coconut fiber are less affected in humid conditions than other hard fibers, resistant to bacteria and saltwater. Globular protrusions make the fiber surface heterogeneous with prominent cracks, micropores, and irregular deposition (Mishra and Basu, 2020a).

Fiber extraction

For Mathai (2005), the fiber can be extracted from the fibrous coconut husk after natural maceration or mechanical extraction. Mechanical extraction by a decorticator has no separation of short and long fibers, while by a comber it has separation of fibers (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Flowchart types of coconut fiber extraction (Adapted from Mathai, 2005).

According to Meenatchisundarm (1979), the husk has 30 -50% fiber, in which the fiber yield is 10 to 17.5%, and 1000 husks can yield about 140kg of fiber. Lignin normally occurs in vascular tissues in fluid transport and mechanical resistance. Fibrillation can be performed by mechanical means and/or chemical treatment. In mechanical pulping, lignin removal is not possible (Akmar et al., 2000).

However, with the increase in demand for ecological materials, the production of brown fiber (from mechanical extraction) has increased from 335 to 459 thousand tons, while there is a reduction in the production of white fiber, from 95 to 81 thousand tons of conventional extraction, in India (Mishra and Basu, 2020a).

Handcrafted and industrial processing

Spinning still does not show advances in mechanization, done by mainly manual methods, 23 varieties of yarn have already been developed and registered in India, in rigid, medium, and soft twists. An estimated 20% of the fibers are being bleached for use, however, the process is carried out in the spinning process due to the bulk of the fiber (Mathai, 2005a). Currently, there are more than 300 variations and ecotypes of coconut in fiber quality and quantity in Southeast Asian countries (Mishra and Basu, 2020b).

Until the development of the study, parameters for commercial industrial use of fiber quality were not established, and no specific machine for precise separation of fibers was established (Mishra and Basu, 2020a).

In Brazil, green coconut husks have a late technology compared to mature coconuts, however, for the processing technology of green coconut husks, Embrapa Agroindústria Tropical has developed equipment for this material (Carvalho, 2009; Correa, 2006b) (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Equipment for processing green coconut shells (Mattos et al., 2013).

After the crushing, pressing, and sorting process, the fibers correspond to 30% of the final product, while the powder corresponds to 70% of the sorting machine (Mattos et al., 2013)

Coconut fiber treatment methods

The fibers have impurities, wax, greasy and globular protrusions on their surface, with detectable cracks and micropores. The main treatments identified in the literature involve (i) alkaline treatment; (ii) acid treatments (HCl, CH₃COOH, HNO₃); (iii) oxidizing treatments (NaOCl, H₂O₂); (iv) treatment with ethylene dimethacrylate (EMA) and UV radiation; (v) treatment involving dinitrophenylation, diazo coupling and combined diazo-cyanoethylation coupling; (vi) urea treatment of acid hydrolyzed and mercerized coconut fiber fibers; and (vii) accelerated chemical softening in the combination of strong reducing agent and alkalis (Bilal et al., 2020; Chiochetta et al., 2017; Khalil et al., 2006; Madhav et al., 2018; Mathai, 2005a; Mishra and Basu, 2020a, 2020b; Nunes et al., 2020).

Fiber processing

In India, the production of fabrics in the coconut industry can be broadly classified as woven and non-woven. Most fabrics are manufactured using simple warp and weft interlacing methods in hand weaving, traditional handlooms, and power loom (Mathai, 2005b, 2005a; Meenatchisundarm, 1979; Mishra and Basu, 2020a).

Applicability of coconut fiber and main products

The production and destination of coconut follow different flows from the main producers and global markets. Brazilian crops are intended for the production of dried coconut *in natura* such as coconut milk, grated coconut, and coconut water, especially in other markets the focus has greater destination on the production of copra, with main derivatives to oil and coconut flour (Brainer and Ximenes, 2020; Simone et al., 2020). In general, dry coconut (solid albumen) is the most used in the fresh consumption of dry pulp, and in industrialization, the production of grated coconut, coconut milk, and derivatives comes from the Giant variety. The green coconut (liquid albumen) for the production of coconut water is obtained from the dwarf variety, also used in the agro-industry, and the hybrid is intended for both purposes, both for the production of dry coconut and green coconut. (Brainer, 2018; Landau, 2018).

Coconut is considered a multipurpose tree. Every part of the coconut tree can be used economically. Throughout history, the emphasis on the part used in coconut shows different use in regions of the world. (Nayar, 2017). The use of the trunk of palm trees is unlikely, and the use of fibers and production of panels and pulp is the only promising way (Akmar et al., 2000). Nonetheless, Mororo (1998), in a base book for the Coconut Industrialization series, states that the uses can happen:

- (1) Log or Spike: It can be used for wood used in joinery, marquetry (inlaid work), floors, ornamental pieces and structural elements in bridges, fences, houses, corrals, and other rural constructions [...]
- (2) Coconut leaves: For covering and walls of native houses, warehouses and nurseries, and/or traced for carpets, panels, hats, fans, fans and other articles. The petiole is used to make baskets, and animal feed [...]
- (3) Coconut tree root: Used for baskets, and by native populations as a toothpaste (roasted and ground roots) for medicinal purposes and as an antiseptic for wounds [...]
- (4) The tender shoots: Consumed in salads as preserves (palm hearts, pickles) [...]
- (5) Inflorescences: A sap known as “tódi” is extracted which is used as refreshment in the regions collected daily (product of natural fermentation) with about 8% alcohol, high as vinegar, sugar and yeast for bread [.. .]
- (6) Coconut: The fruit of the coconut tree is considered the most important and used. Of the more than 100 products, the following are mentioned: (i) whole coconut; copra (dry almonds for oil extraction); (iii) coconut oil (from copra or almond); (iv) coconut cake (oil extraction residue); (v) fibers and other food products (Mororo, 1998, p. 10,11 e 13).

Studies, when not directed to the use of fiber, show that the treatment of coconut palm waste is aimed at transforming it into fertilizers and organic compounds (Nunes, 2011). For Mathai (2005), spinning coconut yarn from coconut fiber has been practiced over the centuries, but its industrial manufacture began in the mid-19th century. Residual by-products of coconut cultivation, especially the fruit, classified as hard fibers, were used in the manufacture of low-value-added products, often considered as waste or residual material. (Regina and Carneiro, 2020; Santana et al., 2020). Over the years, the polymer industry has leveraged its use of materials with sustainable characteristics (Machado et al., 2014). The coconut shell wrapped around the fruit represents the fibrous material, which makes up the internal endocarp (liquid and solid food) and the external mesocarp (fibrous part), and attributes such as fineness and length, and maturity is decisive in its application (Dam, 2002; Madhav et al., 2018; Mishra and Basu, 2020b).

According to the National Association of Coconut Producers in Brazil - APROCOCO, the use of fibers can be diverse, however, when subjected to stripping processing, groups of short fibers are obtained, used as cushion filling material, and long fibers, for industrial brushes. The applicability and use of these fibers cover the manufacture of mattresses; rugs; brooms; filling; wood manufacturing; blankets for reforestation; and packaging, but are commonly applied in gardening and decoration; substrate for seedlings, and the manufacture of vases in Brazil. It is observed that there is not a wide current application of fiber in the textile aspect (APROCOCO, 2021).

Because it is completely absorbed by the soil and its long-lasting qualities, coconut fiber has offered better performance than natural geotextiles in erosion control, soil stabilization, and river protection (Mathai, 2005b).

In order to add value, avoid and/or reduce the negative effect of this residue on the environment, alternatives have been studied. The automobile industry is one of the first industries to use vegetable fibers in its production processes, with the use of natural fiber composites, a viable alternative to the use of synthetic fibers (Jeronimo and Silva, 2013). Composites reinforced by coconut fibers, in addition to the character of biodegradability and ease of composting at the end of their useful life, their production can be done in a simple way and with low energy consumption. In their tests, coconut fiber showed positive results in mechanical properties such as maximum breaking strength, elongation and modulus of elasticity, and better physicochemical interactions between the reinforcement and the matrix (Giacomini, 2017). The use of coconut fiber has been studied as an alternative for obtaining fuels,

allowing for more sustainable economic growth, and avoiding the current energy scenario of depletion (Passos, 2005). By modifying the physical structure and composition of coconut fiber, it is possible to make efficient conversions into glucose viable (Gonçalves et al., 2014) (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Coconut Fiber Applicabilities (Adapted from Dollet et al., 2008; Jeronimo and Silva, 2013; Martins et al., 2013; Wei et al., 2007).

In the literature, studies address the use of coconut fiber in wastewater treatments and, mainly, as a filtering material in organic filters. However, its properties make the material a potential alternative. Green coconut husk fiber ash is an effective adsorbent and has a great potential for adsorption in the treatment of effluents containing iron and aluminum, due to its properties (Catunda et al., 2016; Regina and Carneiro, 2020). The porous morphology also adds to the removal of metals in effluents, due to its surface that allows the adsorption of metals in the interstices present in the material (Silva et al., 2015). The porous morphology also adds to the removal of metals in effluents, due to its surface that allows the adsorption of metals in the interstices present in the material (Monaco et al., 2009).

Finally, studies identify that the possible textile applicability of green coconut fiber involves furniture, footwear, design of objects for the home, composites, paper, and packaging, as well as other areas such as civil construction, enzymes, and geotextiles (Martins et al., 2013).

CONCLUSION

Efficient management, based on sustainable criteria, of agro-industry wastes, requires urgent programs to evaluate methods and new possibilities in the short and long term. The development of appropriate technologies for these processes reduces the sector's negative impacts and increases its eco-efficiency, generating ecological benefits on several fronts, from land use and waste, as well as greater management of the extraction of non-renewable resources. All reported results contributed to a preliminary understanding of the potential use of agro-industrial waste in the generation of industrial textile products in agreement with other industries. The employment of fibers from residual agricultural biomass is a cheap, accessible, and widely available alternative, constituting a model for adding economic value to the agro-industrial chains of the Brazilian main crops.

The analysis of the scientific literature database reveals that research on the recovery and relocation of agro-industrial materials in the textile industry still shows incipient advances in Brazil.

Coconut fibers stand out due to their intense abundance of residues, and their physicochemical properties of high quality, low cost, low density, and biodegradability. Despite being well-known fibers, the industrial applicability of fibers in the Brazilian industry is almost null, while availability is growing. Alternative technologies are generally not introduced to the domestic fiber industry, such as coconut, so far, neglecting their potential to expand an effective research structure, at a possible technological disadvantage compared to other cultures in the country. The coconut crop has great potential for adapting to different crops (such as cocoa and coffee) and climate and soil conditions, an important characteristic for small farmers with limited area.

The research directed to the industry presents a larger incidence focused on treating effluents than applied to new materials, constituting scientific opportunities. Thus, scientific investment in research on materials and technology development is necessary to provide applications that could meet current and future demands and expand the scope of new materials for sustainability.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.

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